

Resonance-focused Energy Group Structure Optimization for a Lead-cooled Fast Reactor

Zachary Bevans¹, Scott Palmtag^{1,*}

¹North Carolina State University, 2500 Stinson Dr, Raleigh, NC, USA

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ABSTRACT

Accurate yet computationally efficient modeling of advanced reactors, such as lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), requires energy group structures that capture spectral features while minimizing computational cost. Traditional fast reactor group structures, such as the ANL33 structure, are largely equal lethargy bins and neglect resonance phenomena unique to specific fast reactor types. This work presents a resonance-focused energy group structure optimization method that generates tailored broad energy group structures for a given fast reactor design. Broad group cross sections for each candidate group structure are generated with the MC²-3 fast reactor multigroup cross section generation code and then employed in Griffin. The methodology is applied to the ALFRED LFR, where 1,725 candidate structures were generated across 13–25 groups. The optimal 22-group structure (LFR22) achieves comparable accuracy to ANL33 in k_{eff} , total leakage rate, and reaction rate distributions, with a substantial reduction in computational time when using CMFD acceleration. Without acceleration, a 33% reduction in computational time and memory for transport calculations is achievable. The resonance-focused approach demonstrates that physics-informed optimization of group structures can substantially improve the efficiency of deterministic transport calculations for fast reactor analysis.

Keywords: energy group structure, LFR, ALFRED, Griffin

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand, countered by little operational experience, for advanced reactors necessitates the need for accurate but efficient modeling and simulation capabilities. A key requirement for the licensing of an advanced reactor design is to ensure that, in the event of an accident, the reactor can be safely shutdown and remain in a controlled state. Safety analysis calculations are then used to understand the behavior of a reactor type under different transient scenarios, and with the substantial increase in computing power, high-fidelity multiphysics reactor simulations are becoming more prevalent to better predict reality. These high-fidelity simulations still remain costly, especially for transient calculations, and increasing performance wherever possible while retaining accuracy is essential.

A common way to alleviate the computational cost of deterministic, high-fidelity radiation transport simulations is utilize coarse energy group structures. Coarse group structures can agree well with the continuous energy solution if they closely represent the true spectrum and an appropriate fine group weighting spectrum is used, but the spectra for these advanced reactor designs are less characterized than conventional light-water reactor systems.

In the case of fast reactor analysis, broad energy group structure choice is limited to structures with energy groups of a single equal lethargy width and are agnostic to a specific reactor design. Because fast reactors widely vary, and consequently their spectrum, tailored energy group structures for each design should be developed. Therefore, this work devises a resonance-focused approach for generating broad energy group structures that are specific to a fast reactor type and has less number of groups than the standard 33-group structure. The approach is then applied to the ALFRED LFR to offer an improved group structure for MOX-fueled LFRs.

*scott_palmtag@ncsu.edu

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Fast Reactor Energy Group Structures

Standard fast reactor energy group structures typically rely on equal lethargy width bins that are simply combined from a finer equal lethargy group structure. For example, the widely accepted ANL33 [1] group structure from Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) uses equal lethargy bins of $\Delta u = 0.50$ from group 2 to 29. The next available coarsest group structure, ANL9, is generated by combining every three groups into one starting from group 7 to group 22. Note that the also commonly used ECCO-33 [2] group structure shares the same group boundaries as the ANL33 for groups 2 through 21. Although the equal lethargy approach agrees with the slowing down nature of neutrons in the fast system, broad group structures (BGXS) with low number of groups ignore resonance phenomena. The resonance features inherent to the LFR energy spectrum is shown by Figure 1 through the neutron flux per unity lethargy with various broad group structures in a fuel assembly located in the central region of the core. The coarser structures average over major resonances that appear in the reference 230-group structure. Moreover, the ANL33 and ANL70 include energy groups in the very fast and thermal ranges where little neutrons reside, which results in unnecessary resolution and higher computational cost.

Figure 1. LFR assembly neutron flux per unit lethargy for various ANL group structures

Inspiration for a tailored group structure for LFRs stems from modern light-water reactor group structures such as the group structures found in VERA/MPACT that originate from a finer group structure like the SCALE-238/252 [3] that explicitly capture important resonances. MPACT offers a 51, 60, and 69 group structure that is specific for a PWR, BWR, and MAGNOX applications, respectively, even though all reactor types are in the thermal spectrum [4, 5]. In most cases, broad group structure optimization involves combining different groups of a pregenerated, finer group structure, but this approach requires that the fine group structure has groups sufficiently small enough to capture resonances or resonance groups are included. Additionally, this approach implies that the BGXS set must have group bounds that match exactly to those of the fine group structure. For fast reactor applications that use deterministic cross section generation tools, cross sections can be condensed from the ultra-fine group structure, such as the ANL2082 or ECCO-2000 (1968 groups), directly. The added flexibility then necessitates a way to effectively limit the search space, as for even a very small number of coarse groups, evaluating every possible combination for 2000 fine group boundaries is computationally intractable.

2.2. Lead-cooled Fast Reactor Design

The prototype Advanced Lead-cooled Fast Reactor European Demonstrator (ALFRED) in development by the FALCON Consortium is the LFR studied in this work. Core design specifications were retrieved from the OECD NEA 2024 LFR benchmark [6]. The ALFRED reactor is a 300 MW_{th} advanced modular reactor with the intended purpose of demonstrating commercial operation as well as providing experimental data for LFR development. ALFRED has 134 hexagonal fuel assemblies surrounded by an additional two rings of shield assemblies. Radial and axial views of ALFRED are presented in Figure 2, where each color represents a unique subassembly type. The total core height is 350 cm, and the active core region is 81 cm. ALFRED uses annular MOX fuel with two fuel types (FINN and FOUT) of different plutonium oxide weight fractions at 20.5% and 26.2%. The remaining fuel is depleted UO₂. Each fuel and shield assembly has 127 fuel pins and an assembly pitch of 16.7 cm. For each assembly, a hexagonal duct surrounds the pins. Reactivity is controlled by enriched B-10 B₄C absorber assemblies that are inserted from below the core. Twelve control rods (FOLW location) are expected to be partially inserted during normal operation and withdrawn as the core depletes. Four additional safety devices (OPEE location) are reserved for shutdown or accident scenarios.

Figure 2. ALFRED core model

2.3. Griffin Reactor Analysis Tool

Neutronics modeling was performed using the Griffin [7] multi-fidelity radiation transport and reactor physics application in development by Idaho National Laboratory and Argonne National Laboratory. Built in the Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) Framework, Griffin is a Finite Element Method based application for the purpose of advanced reactor analysis. Griffin can be easily coupled with other MOOSE-based applications for multiphysics eigenvalue, depletion, or time-dependent simulations. The Discontinuous Finite Element Discrete Ordinates neutron transport solver (DFEM-S_N) was selected for this analysis. In addition to the parallel asynchronous sweeper, the DFEM-S_N solver has the option for generalized CMFD acceleration to speedup the transport calculation.

In addition to Griffin performing neutronics calculations on generalized geometry, Griffin has several

workflows to expedite reactor analysis for various advanced reactor types. In particular, a workflow was developed for liquid-metal fast reactor analysis, where, from a heterogeneous geometry and materials description, both BGXS are generated and a core transport model in a simpler geometry: homogeneous, ring-heterogeneous, and duct-heterogeneous. Moreover, cross sections are mapped to material regions and input files are generated automatically to limit user error.

BGXS generation is handled by the MC²-3 [1] code developed by ANL that is tailored for fast reactor applications and is now integrated into Griffin. MC²-3 solves the slowing down equation in 2082 energy groups on 0D or 1D geometry. In 1D geometry, the Collision Probabilities Method (1D-CPM) is used and is preferred for fuel and control rod assemblies. For control rod assemblies, an additional ring comprised of a fuel composition is added to be the fission source. Following the transport solution, cross sections are condensed from the 2082 group solution to the selected broad group structure.

Region-wise fine group flux spectra can be passed to MC²-3 to correct BGXS with the local flux spectra that is representative of the target core. Spectrum weighting of BGXS for low number of energy groups has proved to greatly improve solution accuracy. Region-wise flux spectra are obtained from a Griffin S_N solve on representative RZ model of the core in many energy groups (≈ 1000).

2.4. Neutronics Model Description

The ALFRED neutronics model in Griffin employed a homogenized assembly geometry approach with six elements per assembly radially. The core was divided into 74 non-uniform axial nodes, with 18 axial nodes in the active core ($\Delta z = 4.50$ cm). Control rod and safety devices were at their fully withdrawn positions. A Gauss-Chebyshev product quadrature was selected with two polar and three azimuthal angles per quadrant, or 48 total directions. A P3 anisotropic scattering approximation was chosen. A uniform coolant density distribution was modeled, and cross sections were evaluated, in accordance to the benchmark specification, at 1200 K for fuel and 600 K for non-fuel materials using the ENDF/B-VII.0 data library. Previous work verified the Griffin model to an exact geometry, continuous energy Serpent Monte Carlo model, and Griffin agreed well with BGXS from MC²-3 for the ANL33 and ANL70 group structures. Noteworthy differences existed when using the ANL9 group structure. To speedup evaluations, heterogeneous cross sections were generated for fuel assemblies only. Reaction rates were tallied for each of the axial nodes in the fuel region only.

3. METHODS

The resonance-focused approach developed in this work aims to reduce the number of energy groups through incorporating resonance features specific to a fast reactor type into the coarse group structure. Since cross sections are condensed from the 2082 group solution in MC²-3 directly, significant freedom exists in generating group boundaries. Because of this, the energy domain is first broken up by selected resonances or user-defined fixed boundaries. Between each resonance or fixed boundary, the interval is split into equal lethargy width bins. Group structures are constructed by defining the maximum number of sub-bins for each interval, and every unique combination possible of binning that sums to a given total number of coarse groups, N_g , are generated. Therefore, the number of combinations is dictated by the maximum sub-binning and resonances. An example of the energy binning for $N_g=10$ is illustrated in Figure 3 where green bins represent a resonance group, red is a user-defined fixed boundary, and Δu_x is the uniform lethargy width in an interval.

Currently, resonance widths and fixed energy bounds are provided by the user. The method is flexible to where any number of resonances can be provided, but including many isotopes with several resonances such as SCALE-238/252 group structures can quickly lead to expensive calculations. Therefore, resonances are chosen based on the observed fine group core spectrum. Using the original ALFRED Serpent model, spectra were tallied with the ANL230 group structure in both the fuel and periphery assemblies to ensure that resonances that may show up in non-fueled regions are also considered. Sim-

Figure 3. Energy group binning combinations for $N_g = 10$

ilarly, fixed boundaries were selected based on the flux spectrum to allow for more control between resonances. The resonance and fixed energy boundaries were matched exactly with the ANL230 solution. From the spectrum in Figure 1, the energy bounds for the resonances and fixed boundaries used in the optimization for ALFRED are provided in Table I. With five resonances and three fixed boundaries, the smallest possible group structure has 13 energy groups.

Table I. Resonances used in group structure optimization

	Number	Lower energy bound (MeV)	Upper energy bound (MeV)	Lethargy width (Δu)
Resonance	1	3.6883E-01	4.7359E-01	0.250
	2	1.7422E-01	1.8316E-01	0.050
	3	1.2907E-01	1.3569E-01	0.050
	4	2.6058E-02	3.1828E-02	0.200
	5	2.3579E-02	2.6058E-02	0.100
Fixed Boundary	1	-	3.6788E+00*	-
	2	-	4.5400E-04 [†]	-
	3	-	5.0453E-06 [‡]	-

* ANL33 group 4, [†] ANL9 group 8, [‡] ANL9 group 9

For each candidate group structure, the group boundaries are passed to Griffin to generate the BGXS and then once complete, the 3D full-core eigenvalue calculation is performed. To ensure that error only exists due to energy group discretization, the candidate solutions are compared to the equivalent Griffin model using the ANL230 fine group solution. Metrics compared include the critical eigenvalue, total leakage rate, and 3D one-group fission (Σ_{fission}) and total (Σ_{total}) reaction rate distributions. Reaction rates were tallied in each axial node in the active core region for each fuel assembly. For a given number of coarse groups, the best candidate solution was chosen using Lexicographic Sorting, which is a priority-based multiobjective optimization algorithm that is always Pareto optimal. The priority metrics used, in order, were: 3D Σ_{fission} , Δk_{eff} , $\Delta \text{Leakage rate}$, 3D Σ_{total} . A priority based method was selected since the fission reaction rate can be favored as it directly relates to the reactor power profile. Furthermore, previous verification exercises demonstrated that Σ_{fission} exhibited the most difference from Monte Carlo when using a coarse group structure.

4. RESULTS

With the desire to develop a physics-based energy group structure that performs equally as well as the ANL33 group structure for the ALFRED LFR in less number of energy groups, energy group structures for 13 up to 25 total number of energy groups were generated with the resonance-focused approach. With the selected maximum sub-bins per interval for the resonances and fixed bounds established in Table I, a total of 1725 unique energy group structures were evaluated. Each evaluation required approximately 20 minutes for both the BGXS generation and full-core eigenvalue calculation. The RZ calculation was once, and currently, MC²-3 calculations are executed in serial. Each eigenvalue calculation was carried out with 96 processors on the INL HPC machines. The metrics compared to the Griffin ANL230 group solution for every evaluated group structure are illustrated in Figure 4. The ANL9 and ANL33 values for each metric are also included as a benchmark for the devised structures.

Figure 4. Compared metrics for all group structures

Low error is achieved with 20 energy groups or more and perform almost equally as well as the ANL33. After 20 energy groups, error in the fission reaction rate RMSE stagnated, which is a result of the provided maximum number of sub-binning. After 20 groups, the lower energy regions hit their maximum possible sub-bins. Regardless, the difference in RMSE between the 33-group solution is around 0.08%. Similarly, the total reaction rate does not reach the ANL33 but differs by only 0.04%. Total leakage rate prediction continues to improve as more energy groups are added, and the developed group structures outperform the ANL33 after 22 groups. The large deviations in results for a given number of energy groups also demonstrate how poor energy group boundary choice can lead to inaccurate predictions.

Table II. Best group structure results for each number of groups

Coarse energy groups (N_g)	3D fission reaction rate RMSE (%)	Δk_{eff} (pcm)	Δ Leakage rate (rel. %)	3D total reaction rate RMSE (%)	Execution time (sec)	Speedup t_{ANL33} / t_g
13	1.378	37.6	4.817	0.360	306	6.29
14	0.824	-15.9	3.212	0.229	329	5.85
15	0.711	-4.8	3.075	0.236	355	5.43
16	0.586	-19.1	2.535	0.214	382	5.04
17	0.373	-15.5	2.765	0.250	411	4.69
18	0.381	-2.3	2.318	0.163	442	4.39
19	0.378	-2.1	2.149	0.151	473	4.07
20	0.229	-18.1	2.111	0.131	500	3.85
21	0.227	4.1	1.617	0.123	537	3.59
22	0.223	4.3	1.448	0.112	565	3.41
23	0.222	3.9	1.388	0.108	596	3.23
24	0.222	-1.1	1.199	0.115	622	3.10
25	0.221	-1.5	1.140	0.111	635	3.03
ANL9	0.802	4.6	2.877	0.210	218	8.83
ANL33	0.142	12.1	1.390	0.079	1926	-

The Lexicographic Sorting algorithm was then utilized to select the best candidate solution for each total number of groups. The compared metrics for the best group structures are summarized in Table II along with the execution time and speedup compared to ANL33. The ANL9 and ANL33 are again included for comparison. The 22-group structure, LFR22, was decided to be the best group structure as it balances solution accuracy and execution time. Over a three times speedup is observed over the ANL33, but this is a result of the CMFD solution taking longer than the transport sweep between non-linear iterations for the 33-group calculation. In the unaccelerated case, a 33% reduction in runtime and memory is expected, as both values are linear when using S_N . Overall, the devised group structures compare very closely to the 33-group solution while noticeably reducing wall time and required resources.

Figure 5. LFR22 energy group boundaries

The energy group boundaries for the LFR22 group structure are overlaid on the 230-group spectrum in Figure 5. The LFR22 group structure was also verified against the 3D full-core, exact geometry, CE Serpent model, which performed slightly better than the ANL33. Note, the 3D maximum reaction rate difference is the maximum axial nodal difference in normalized reaction rate throughout the entire active core region.

Table III. LFR22 comparison to Serpent

Model	ANL9	ANL33	LFR22
k_{eff}^*	1.07597	1.07604	1.07591
Δk_{eff} (pcm)	535	545	532
Δ Leakage rate (rel. %)	2.62	-0.26	0.33
3D Σ_{fission} RMSE (%)	0.79	0.48	0.44
3D Σ_{fission} max diff. (%)	-3.25	-1.14	-1.13
3D Σ_{total} RMSE (%)	0.26	0.36	0.27
3D Σ_{total} max diff. (%)	0.81	0.84	0.69

* Serpent $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.07059 \pm 0.2$ pcm

5. CONCLUSIONS

Using the resonance-focused approach, energy group structures were developed that consider the resonance features of MOX-fueled LFRs and compare very well to the fine group solution. From generating 1725 unique candidate group structures from 13 to 25 total energy groups, the best 22-group structure was selected as the most optimum. The 22-group structure sped up the CMFD-accelerated transport solution by a factor greater than three over the standard ANL33 group structure, while achieving similar solution accuracy. For unaccelerated transport calculations, a 33% reduction in runtime and memory is expected. Consequently, the substantial reduction in resources significantly eases the computation burden associated high-fidelity multiphysics simulation of LFRs. Future work can include investigating the sensitivity in optimum solution with respect to optimization parameters such as resonance selection or optimization metrics. Furthermore, this methodology would benefit from implementing an algorithm to better determine influential resonances and incorporating an optimization algorithm such as Simulated Annealing or Genetic Algorithm.

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